

A STUDY OF JOB SATISFACTION LEVEL OF GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS OF PUNJAB

Dr. Inderpreet Kaur

Principal, University Institute of Teachers Training and Research, Chandigarh University,
Gharuan, Punjab

Cite This Article: Dr. Inderpreet Kaur, "A Study of Job Satisfaction Level Of Government and Private Senior Secondary School Teachers of Punjab", International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 386-392, 2018.

Copy Right: © IJCRME, 2018 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

The development of young people in our society depends on the skill, knowledge, and caring of practicing professional's i.e teachers. Attending to the quality of schooling is fundamental to concerns for equity, opportunity, and the growth of human potential. In recent years, both teaching and the professional education designed to develop it have come under fire. This study is an evaluative and diagnostic attempt to discover empirically the nature of relationships between job satisfaction in two areas. The sample comprised of 600 secondary school teachers working in government and private schools in five districts of Punjab .Job satisfaction have been taken on two areas. Job intrinsic and job extrinsic aspects. Job intrinsic aspects include job concrete, and job abstract. Job extrinsic aspects include psycho-social, economic and community growth. The analysis revealed that each of these aspects played a important role in job satisfaction. This may be interpreted that Government and Private Secondary School teachers have same opinion on job concrete, job abstract and community growth, but differ in psycho social and economic aspects of job satisfaction. Which is very important for teacher effectiveness which ultimately affects student achievement?

Key Words: Education & Job Satisfaction

Introduction:

Education is the most crucial investment in human resource development. The quality of manpower in any nation ultimately determines the sustainable well being of its people. Education has been a determining factor in achieving rapid development and technological progress and is the principle instrument for developing human capabilities for creation of social order based on values of freedom, social justice and equal opportunity.

The quality of school education is one of the most important indicators for development, since high level of knowledge, competencies and skills are considered to be the very basic condition of active citizenship, employment, and social cohesion. Further, school quality affects students learning through training and talent of teaching force, what goes on in the classrooms and the overall culture and atmosphere of the school. Teachers acts as mentors pursuing all round development of learners and have the highest influence on the evolution of the society. The importance of teachers in the educational process is unquestionable. Obtaining capable teachers is an intrinsic unrest and obtaining capable teachers is an intrinsic interest and obligation of education. If competent teachers can be obtained, the likelihood of attaining desirable educational outcomes is substantial.

Education is an essential concomitant of all human societies. In the overall paradigm of development, education is an important index of human resource development. It is the innermost call of human kind to evolve, innovate and reach its pinnacle. Education is the organized and sustained instruction designed to communicate a combination of knowledge, skills and understanding valuables for all the activities of life. It is universally acknowledged as the master key that alone can open the doors to peace, progress and prosperity, thereby providing the most powerful strategy to face the challenges that the future holds in store for human beings.

The persons who are largely responsible for the fortune of these enterprises are the teachers. Teacher is the cornerstone of the arch of education. Delor's Report (1996) further says, "You cannot have good school unless you have good teachers. The two are inseparable, it is impossible to have high quality education unless there are high quality teachers" The success of educational process depends to a great extent on the character and ability of the teachers.

The most common way of determining an employee's satisfaction with a job is to ask that person if he is satisfied with the work to which he is engaged. From this point of view, "Job satisfaction is any combination of psychological, physiological and environmental circumstances that causes a person truthfully to say, "I am satisfied with my job." Job satisfaction refers to an overall effective orientation on the part of individuals towards their work roles, which they are presently occupying. This conceptualization implies that job satisfaction is a unitary concept, and that individuals may characterized by some sort of vaguely defined attitude towards their total job satisfaction. Job satisfaction being a unitary concept does not imply that causes of this

overall attitude are not multidimensional. Obviously, a person may be satisfied with one dimension of the job and dissatisfied with another

According to Colbert and Wolff (1992), 50% of new teachers drop out of the profession during the first five years. Many teachers dropped out of the profession for a plethora of reasons. Teachers felt that the profession was not valued by society, the demands and accountability increased, and an overabundance of stress all played significant roles in how teachers viewed their jobs and the satisfaction they received from it (Latham, 1998).

According to Bishay (1996), the teaching profession ranks high on the success list of a society. In conjunction with this, "teachers' organisational commitment and general job satisfaction" (Howell & Dorfman, 1986) have been identified as important to understanding the work behaviour of employees in organisations. Job satisfaction amongst teachers is a multifaceted construct that is critical to teacher retention and has been shown to be a significant determinant of teacher commitment, and in turn, a contributor to school effectiveness. Research, however, reveals wide-ranging differences in what contributes to job satisfaction and group differences according to demographic factors (Shan, 1998).

Job Satisfaction

Work plays a tremendous role in people's lives, as it is a significant source of income, personal realization, personal and professional improvement. Because of the central role that work occupies in many people's life, satisfaction with one's job is an important component in overall wellbeing. Job satisfaction has been a topic of great interest for researchers and practitioners in a wide range of fields including organizational psychology, public administration, and management

Job Satisfaction:

Job satisfaction is a favourableness with which workers view their job. It results when there is a fit between job requirements and the wants and expectations of employee. In other words, it expresses the extent of match between worker's expectations and the rewards the job provides and the values it creates and gets cherished.

Buitendach and de Witte (2005) proffer the view that job satisfaction relates to an individual's perceptions and evaluations of a job, and this perception is in turn influenced by their circumstances, including needs, values and expectations. Individuals therefore evaluate their jobs on the basis of factors which they regard as being important to them (Sempene, Rieger & Roodt, 2002).

Reio and Kidd (2006) defined job satisfaction as "the feelings a worker has about his or her job or job experiences in relation to previous experience, current expectations, or available alternatives"

From the above definitions, it can be concluded that job satisfaction is a positive feeling towards the work. It is a positive emotional state that occurs when a person's job seems to fulfill important job values, provided these values are compatible with one's needs. Educational researchers have become increasingly interested in determining not only the degree of job satisfaction among teachers but also the source of their job satisfaction and dissatisfaction. The primary source of job satisfaction is recognition, achievement and works itself. Sometimes, there are work centered factors that provide for self fuelling, self actualizing, and job enrichment experiences for them.

Review of Literature:

Biswas and Tinku (1994) examined the job satisfaction of 124 secondary school teachers in relation to some variables like male-female, urban-rural areas, Govt. and primary schools. Following major conclusions were drawn from the study:

- ✓ Secondary female teachers differed significantly in job satisfaction from their male counterparts.
- ✓ Urban teachers perceived greater satisfaction in monetary and other physical facilities available and lesser satisfaction in service and personal security, as compared to teachers from rural areas.
- ✓ Teachers serving in privately managed schools perceived greater job satisfaction in respect to human relationships, than teachers in government schools.

Khatoon (2000) examined the Job satisfaction of sec. school teachers in relation to their personal variables. A sample of 228 secondary school teachers was taken. Job satisfaction scale by Verma (1972) was used for the collection of data. The findings of the study showed that majority of the teachers were satisfied from their jobs. The female teachers had a greater job satisfaction than the male teachers. Fresher teachers were more satisfied than the more experienced teachers.

Ahmad (2003) examined the job satisfaction of teachers. 236 teachers, teaching in senior secondary schools of Aligarh were taken as a sample. Following conclusions were drawn from the study:

- ✓ Female teachers enjoyed greater job satisfaction than their male counterparts.
- ✓ The married teachers showed more job satisfaction than unmarried teachers.
- ✓ Teachers who were teaching in government schools showed greater job satisfaction than teachers teaching in private schools.
- ✓ There was no significant change in the job satisfaction due to change in the level of independent variables like sex, marital status and types of schools.

Ayishabi and Amruth (2005) did a study on job satisfaction of primary school teachers in relation to their teaching competence. It was found that the relationship between teaching competence and job satisfaction was positive and significant and that relationship was not influenced by sex, locale, teaching experience and educational qualification.

Crossman and Harris (2006) examined job satisfaction among secondary school teachers in different types of secondary schools. The results indicate a significant difference in the overall job satisfaction scores of teachers by type of school. Teachers in independent and privately managed schools exhibited the highest satisfaction levels while those in foundation schools exhibited the lowest. No significant difference in satisfaction was found when the data were analysed by age, gender and length of service.

Hollyene Celeste Turner (2007) made an attempt to study the Predictors of Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Urban Middle Schools in North Carolina. The study was conducted on 46 middle schools with 2,900 teachers. It was found that teachers' main concerns in relation to job satisfaction revolved around time, facilities and resources, and moderately around empowerment and professional development.

Nobile (2008) examined the relationships between the biographical characteristics gender, age, years of experience and employment position, and job satisfaction of staff members in Catholic primary schools and it was found that Age, gender and position were related to a number of facets of job satisfaction as well as overall job satisfaction. No significant relationships were identified for years of experience. This study includes non-teaching staff and investigates the role of employment position as a biographical variable

Meager (2011) analysed the characteristics of effective professional development and how those characteristics are associated with teacher job satisfaction and teacher working conditions and found that the association between teacher professional development and teacher job satisfaction was not significant.

Mahajan (2015) found that teachers who are above 40 and belong to High socio-economic-status age were highly satisfied on their job satisfaction level as compared to their counterparts with less than 40 years. Male and female differ at this level and Correlation between job satisfaction and life satisfaction of high school teachers was found to be significant and positively related in respect of their age, gender and socio-economic criteria.

From the research studies related to job satisfaction it is concluded that (a) job satisfaction is high among the government school teachers as compared to private school teachers (b) male teachers are more satisfied than female teachers (c) urban teachers are more satisfied as compared to rural teachers (d) teaching competencies, experience of the teacher, educational qualification, atmosphere of the school affect the job satisfaction of the teacher. After reviewing the studies related to job satisfaction the investigator is prompted to undertake a study on the problem in hand.

Methods and Procedures:

The sampling technique employed in accordance with the objectives of the study, was random and purposive in nature. The sampling was purposive as sample was drawn from the schools which were affiliated to Punjab School Education Board. The main purpose to take government as well as private schools in the study was to have a fair representation of all strata in the society. The present study was conducted on 600 secondary school teachers, of government and private schools of five districts of Punjab. With equal number of teachers (300) were selected. Five districts were selected to collect the sample and the districts are northern Part: Hoshiarpur, southern part: Mansa, eastern part: Ropar, western part: Faridkot and south eastern part: Patiala. These districts were purposely selected so that the sample becomes representative of the population

Research Tools:

The following tools were used for the collection of the data. Job Satisfaction Scale by Dr. Amar Singh and Dr. T. R. Sharma (1999)

Objective:

- ✓ To compare the Job satisfaction level of secondary school teachers of government and private schools in terms of intrinsic areas of job satisfaction.
- ✓ To compare the Job satisfaction level of secondary school teachers of government and private schools in terms extrinsic areas of job satisfaction.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction in terms of job extrinsic and job intrinsic areas.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with respect to intrinsic job satisfaction areas in terms of job concrete.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with respect to intrinsic job satisfaction areas in terms of job abstract.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with respect to extrinsic job satisfaction areas in terms of psycho social components.
- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with respect to extrinsic job satisfaction areas in terms of economic components.

- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with respect to extrinsic job satisfaction areas in terms of community growth aspect.

Delimitations:

- ✓ The present study was delimited to the teachers of secondary schools in Punjab only.
- ✓ The present study was restricted to only five districts of Punjab namely: northern Part - Hoshiarpur, southern part –Mansa, eastern part –Ropar, western part- Faridkot, south eastern part-Patiala.
- ✓ The study was delimited to only 600 secondary school teachers of government and private schools.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

The purpose of the present study was to find out the perception on job satisfaction and its area on teachers of senior secondary schools of government as well as private in the state of Punjab. In order to screen the data for meaningful purpose and to test the hypothesis, the data was analyzed by using various statistical techniques. Results were obtained with the help of statistical tools, like independent t-test, one way ANOVA.

Table 1.1: Frequency distribution of Total Job Satisfaction scores for Government and Private senior secondary schools

Class Interval	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent Frequency
96-100	1	0.17	100
91-95	18	3.0	99.8
86-90	184	30.67	96.8
81-85	273	45.5	66.2
76-80	87	14.5	20.7
71-75	26	4.33	6.20
65-70	11	1.83	1.8

Table 1.1 shows the frequency distribution for total job satisfaction score of government and private senior secondary schools. It is clear that most of score lies between 81-85 and 86-90 intervals and very less score were found for 96-100 interval.

Table 1.2: Means, S.D's, Skewness, Kurtosis, Minimum and Maximum of total Job Satisfaction score of Government and Private senior secondary school

Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	Minimum	Maximum
83.4	4.6	-0.54	0.99	68	96

Table 1.2 shows the descriptive statistics of total job satisfaction scores of government and private senior secondary school; Mean, and SD were 83.4 and 4.6 respectively. The value of skewness was -0.54, which showed the distribution is negatively skewed and is less than ± 1 . This value is within the acceptable limit of normality and may be acceptable as having skewness of moderate degree and the value of Kurtosis was 0.99; which indicated that the curve was leptokurtic. Thus, it may indicate towards the fact that distribution of job satisfaction score for teachers is approximated to normal distribution. Maximum and minimum scores of job satisfaction scores were 96 and 68 respectively.

Table reveals that 20.66 % of school teacher showed job satisfaction score up to 76-80 on 65-96 intervals. There is 20.7% scores lies between 76-80. Cumulative percent frequency curve for job satisfaction is shown in Figure 1.1

Figure 1.1: Cumulative Percentage Frequency Polygon of Job Satisfaction of Government and Private Schools

There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction is accepted. It may be inferred that job satisfaction scores of teachers of both schools

were same. Mean difference was further investigated with the help of t-ratio. The means, SD and t-ratio among schools for job satisfaction score have been represented in Table 1.3

Table 1.3: T-value for the significance of difference between the mean of Job Satisfaction scores of Government and Private Schools

	Government (n=300)		Private (n=300)		t value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Job Satisfaction					-0.95

It was revealed that mean and SD values of job satisfaction scores of government schools are 83.3 and 4.5 and 83.6 and 4.6 for private schools. The t value for mean difference was -0.95 which shows no significance between government and private schools.

Table 1.4: T-value for the significance of difference between the mean of Job Concrete scores of Government and Private Schools

	Government (n=300)		Private (n=300)		t value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Job Concrete	17.8	2.4	18.0	2.3	-1.38

It was revealed that mean and SD values of job concrete scores of government schools are 17.8 and 2.4 and 18.0 and 2.3 for private schools. The t value for mean difference was -1.38 which shows no significance between government and private schools.

Table 1.5: The t-value for the significance of difference between the mean of job abstract scores of Government and Private school

	Government (n=300)		Private (n=300)		t value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Job Abstract	17.54	1.31	17.46	1.27	0.76

It was found that Mean and SD value of job s abstract scores of Government are 17.54 and 1.31 & 17.46 and 1.27 for Private school. The t value for mean difference was 0.76 which shows no significance between Government and Private school. Mean comparison of job abstract scores between Government and Private schools is shown in Figure 4.26.

Table 1.6: F -value for the significance of difference between mean private & government school and streams for the psycho-social scores

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F value	p value
School	53.9	1	53.9	4.5	0.04*
Stream	890.1	2	445	37	0.00**
School * stream	136.9	2	68.5	5.68	0.00**
Error	7152.3	594	12		
Total	189653	600			

**p<0.01,* p<0.05

School: Government and Private

Stream: Language, Science/Math & Social science

Table 4.43 indicates that school showed significant mean difference (F=4.50 & p<0.05) at 0.05 level of significance. It showed that the mean of psycho-social score of Government and Private schools was different.

Table 1.6: The t-value for the significance of difference between the mean of psycho-social scores of Government and Private school

	Government (n=300)		Private (n=300)		t value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Psycho-Social	17.7	3.8	17.1	3.6	1.93

It was revealed that Mean and SD value of psycho-social scores of Government are 17.7 and 3.8 & 17.1 and 3.6 for Private school. The t value for mean difference was 1.93 which shows no significance between Government and Private school.

Table 1.7: The t-value for the significance of difference between the mean of economic scores of Government and Private school

	Government (n=300)		Private (n=300)		t value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Economic Scores	11.7	1.6	11.5	1.6	1.54

It was revealed that Mean and SD value of economic scores of Government are 11.7 and 1.6 & 11.5 and 1.6 for Private school. The t value for mean difference was 1.54 which shows no significance between

Government and Private school. Mean comparison of economic scores between Government and Private schools is shown in Figure 4.32.

Table 1.8: The t-value for the significance of difference between the mean of community growth scores of Government and Private school

	Government (n=300)		Private (n=300)		t value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Economic Scores	18.5	4.2	19.1	3.9	-1.61

It was revealed that Mean and SD value of community growth scores of Government are 18.5 and 4.2 & 19.1 and 3.9 for Private school. The t value for mean difference was -1.61 which shows no significance between Government and Private school.

Conclusion:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with respect to job satisfaction. It was revealed that mean and SD value of job satisfaction of government secondary school teachers are 83.3 and 4.5 and 83.6 and 4.6 for private secondary school teachers. The t-value for mean difference was -0.95 which shows no significant difference between government and private schools.
- ✓ The results clearly indicate that there is no significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with regard to different areas of job satisfaction namely job concrete, job abstract, economic and community growth.
- ✓ There is significant difference between government and private secondary school teachers with respect to psycho social area of job satisfaction. The results indicate that both the schools showed significant mean difference ($f=4.50$ and $p<0.05$) at 0.05 level of significance. The teachers of both schools have comparable difference in intelligence and their social circle.
- ✓ The secondary school teachers of government and private schools exhibited same opinion on global job satisfaction and in its areas such as job-concrete, job-abstract, psycho-social and community growth areas. But government teachers exhibited better job satisfaction related to economic factors as compared to their private school counterparts.

References:

1. Ahmad, N., Raheem A., Jamal S. (2003) Job satisfaction among School Teachers. The Educational Review, 46(7).
2. Ayishabi, T.C. and Amruth, G.K. (2005) Job Satisfaction of Primary School Teachers in Relation to Their Teaching Competence. Journal of All India Association for Educational Research, 17(1 and 2), 106-107.
3. Bishay, A. (1996) Teacher Motivation and Job Satisfaction: A Study Employing the Experience Sampling Method. Journal of Undergraduate Sciences, 3, 147-154
4. Biswas P.C. and De, T., (1994), "A study of Job Satisfaction of secondary teachers in relation to some background variables". Journal of Educational Research and Extension, 30(3); 153-163.
5. Buitendach, J. and de Witte, H. (2005) Job Insecurity, Extrinsic and Intrinsic Job Satisfaction and Affective Organisational Commitment of Maintenance Workers in a Parastatal. South African Journal of Business Management, 36(2), 27-37.
6. Colbert, J. and Wolff, D. (1992) Surviving in Urban Schools. Journal of Teacher Education, 43, 193-199.
7. Crossman, A. and Harris (2006) Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers, School of Management, University of Surrey, Guilford, Surrey GU2 7XH, U.K, Educational Management Administration and Leadership, 34(1), 29-46
8. Delors, J. (1996) Learning the Treasure Within. Report to UNESCO of the International Commission on Education for the Twenty-First Century, Paris.
9. Hollyene, C.T. (2007) Predictors of Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Urban Middle Schools. Ph.D. Thesis in Education, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill
10. Howell, J. P. and Dorfman, P. W. (1986) Leadership and substitutes for leadership among professional and nonprofessional workers. The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science, 22, 29-46.
11. John. McCormick, (2008) "Job satisfaction of Catholic primary school staff: a study of biographical differences", International Journal of Educational Management, Vol. 22 Issue: 2, pp.135-150.
12. Khatoun, T. and Hasan, Z. (2000) Job Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in Relation to Their Personal Variables. Indian Educational Psychology Review, 36, 64-73.
13. Latham, A. (1998) Teacher Satisfaction. Educational Leadership, 68, 123 - 126.
14. Meagher, T. (2011) An Investigation of the Relationships of Teacher Professional Development, Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teacher Working Conditions. Dissertations, Paper 68.

15. Reio, T.G. Jr. and Kidd, C.A. (2006) An Exploration of the Impact of Employee Job Satisfaction, Affect, Job Performance, and Organizational Financial Performance: A Review of the Literature. Kentucky: University of Louisville
16. Sempene, M., Rieger, H. & Roodt, G. 2002. 'Job satisfaction in relation to organisational culture', South African Journal of Industrial Psychology, 28(2): 23–30.
17. Shann, M. (1998) Professional Commitment and Satisfaction among Teachers in Urban Middle Schools. The Journal of Educational Research, 92, 67-75.
18. Smith T.W. (2007). Job satisfaction in United States. NORC.University of Chicago